

Impact of three different Intracanal Medicaments on Fracture Resistance of Two different Endodontic Sealers To Root Dentin: An In Vitro Study

Key words- Intracanal medicament, Root canal sealer, Fracture resistance, Radicular Dentin

ABSTRACT

The success of endodontic treatment depends not only on effective elimination of microorganisms but also on the preservation of root dentin integrity, which is essential for long-term tooth survival. Intracanal medicaments such as calcium hydroxide, triple antibiotic paste, and chlorhexidine are routinely used for disinfection; however, prolonged contact may alter dentin's structural and mechanical properties. Similarly, the choice of endodontic sealer plays a vital role in reinforcing or compromising dentin integrity. Few studies have comparatively analyzed the effect of intracanal medicaments on root dentin integrity in the presence of different sealers.

The objective of this in vitro study was to evaluate the effect of Triple Antibiotic Paste, Fosfomycin, Cefixime based TAP used intracanal medicaments on the fracture resistance of root dentin when obturated with two endodontic sealers—Bioceramic-based and epoxy resin-based—through assessment of fracture resistance and structural changes.

CONCLUSION

Introduction

Root canal treatment aims to eliminate intracanal infection and achieve a hermetic seal, while maintaining the structural integrity and fracture resistance of root dentin. Intracanal medicaments such as calcium hydroxide and antibiotic combinations are routinely used to enhance disinfection, but they may alter dentin properties and the interaction between sealer and root dentin, which can influence fracture resistance. Different endodontic sealers (for example, epoxy-resin-based and calcium-silicate-based) also have varying adhesion and reinforcing effects on root dentin, and their performance may be modified by prior use of intracanal medicaments.

Consequently, the bacteria are usually eradicated by using triple antibiotic paste (TAP), a mixture of metronidazole, ciprofloxacin, and minocycline. Triple antibiotic paste (TAP) has been found to have antimicrobial properties and to be biocompatible. It has been discovered to be effective both in vitro and in vivo, and it has been demonstrated to be an efficient combination in eliminating root canal bacteria.

Triple antibiotic paste (TAP), which is a combination of three antibiotics, namely, metronidazole, ciprofloxacin, and minocycline, has been used as an intracanal medicament owing to its high antimicrobial effects. There is a controversy between the studies supporting its efficacy to eradicate *Enterobacteriaceae Faecalis* (EF) in the root canal system completely. This may be due to emerging bacterial resistance. Another drawback of TAP is the crown discoloration due to its minocycline. Therefore, there has been a modification of TAP called modified triple antibiotic paste (MTAP) by replacing minocycline with clindamycin. MTAP was shown to be as effective as TAP in reducing EF in the root canal system. Due to those mentioned drawbacks of TAP and its modification to MTAP, there was a need for a new medicament that has less possibility of resistance, is equivalently potent against EF, and is preferably a single drug, so it needs less time and effort to prepare, is additionally cost-effective, and is a single drug rather than a multidrug.

Nitrofurantoin, an artificial nitrofurane molecule, effectively targets both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and is commonly used in conjunction with oral antibiotics to treat urinary tract infections (UTIs). It is the preferred medication for infections brought on by microorganisms resistant to many drugs. In research involving 300 *Enterococcus* isolates, including *E. faecalis*, none of the isolates exhibited nitrofurantoin resistance. Numerous investigations have shown that nitrofurantoin is highly efficient against *E. faecalis*.

Fosfomycin, a broad-spectrum bactericidal antibiotic, was discovered in 1969 at the Spanish Penicillin and Antibiotics Company and is made by the bacterium *Streptomyces Fradiae*. It is a FDA-approved drug with a trade name of "MONUROL", effective against both gram +ve and gram -ve bacteria. It is widely employed in treating *E. coli* and *E. faecalis*-related uncomplicated urinary tract infections. Fosfomycin can also be produced synthetically. For oral administration, it comes as calcium or trometamol salt [8] and for intravenous administration (it comes as a disodium salt). An oral dosage of 3 grammes is advised based on the safety profile. Chemically, it prevents the production of the cell wall in its initial stages by inhibiting the precursor UDPMurNAc formation which is considered as the primary stage in the formation of microbial cell wall. It catalyzes the transmission of Enol pyruvyl fraction of PEP to the 3'-hydroxyl group of UDP-N-acetylglucosamine, UDP-N-acetylglucosamine enol pyruvyl transferase (MurA) is specifically engaged in peptidoglycan biosynthesis. Fosfomycin inactivates MurA by attaching to the thiol group of a cysteine. Compared to the actions of other drugs, this inhibitory action of this drug occurs early. Fosfomycin, in addition, decreases bacterial adhesion to epithelial cells and also inhibits platelet activator factor, which lessens its adherence of other bacteria like *Haemophilus influenzae* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. Considering these factors, our study aimed to evaluate whether pretreatment of root dentin with three different intracanal medicaments causes any significant changes in the fracture resistance of root dentin obturated with two different endodontic sealers in an in vitro study.

Material And methods

Study design- In vitro experimental study evaluating fracture resistance of decoronated, instrumented human single-rooted teeth after intracanal medicament application and obturation with two different sealers.

Sample size- Total of 60 extracted human single-rooted premolars, distributed into 3 groups (n = 20 each): 3 medicament conditions (medicament 1, medicament 2, medicament 3) × 2 sealers. Sample size may be calculated using standard formulas for comparison of means with reference to previous fracture-resistance or push-out studies.

Eligibility criteria-

Human single rooted mandibular premolar teeth were included the study

Teeth affected with extensive caries, fractured root were excluded from the study.

Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional review board of the college . The study was an in vitro experimental study in which Sample preparation was carried out in the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics; fracture testing performed using a universal testing machine in an accredited materials testing laboratory.

Eligible teeth will be randomly assigned to the 3 groups using simple random sampling (lottery method).

Interventional groups- Total of 60 extracted human single-rooted premolars, were randomly allocated into 3 groups (n = 20 each): which were further divided into 2 subgroups.

Group 1 consisted of triple antibiotic paste, group 2 contained nitrofurantoin, group 3 contained fosfomycin. Each group consisted of 2 subgroups of AH Plus and Cerafill BC.

Group 1

Commercially available Metronidazole, Ciprofloxacin and minocycline tablets were crushed into powder form in mortar pestle and mixed in 1:1:1 ratio and Normal saline was added to achieve paste like consistency. This paste was placed with lentulo spiral upto the working length, canals were then sealed coronally with temporary restorative material.

Group 1A: TAP + AH Plus.

Group 1B: TAP + Cerafill BC

Group 2

Commercially available nitrofurantoin Tablet was crushed and mixed with normal saline and placed with lentulo spiral upto the working length, canals were then sealed coronally with temporary restorative material.

Group 2A: Nitrofurantoin + AH Plus.

Group 2B: Nitrofurantoin + Cerafill BC

Group 3

Commercially available fosfomycin was powdered and combined with saline and placed with lentulo spiral upto the working length, canals were then sealed coronally with temporary restorative material.

Group 3A: Fosfomycin + AH Plus.

Group 3B: Fosfomycin + Cerafill BC

Intracanal Medicament Protocol

- Selected medicaments were placed with lentulo spiral upto the working length, canals were then sealed coronally with temporary restorative material.
- Samples were stored at 37°C and 100% humidity for 14 days.
- Medicament was then removed using hand files and copious irrigation was done with sodium hypochlorite and EDTA, followed by saline; after which the canals were dried.

Obturation

- Canals were obturated using AH PLUS or Cerafill BC with matched-taper single-cone gutta-percha technique according to manufacturer's instructions.
- Roots were stored at 37°C and 100% humidity for 7 days to allow complete setting of sealers.

Fracture Resistance Testing

- Roots were embedded in acrylic or resin blocks leaving 1–2 mm of root exposed above the embedding medium to simulate alveolar bone level.
- A compressive load was applied along the long axis of each root in a universal testing machine at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min until fracture; maximum load at fracture was recorded in Newtons.

Outcome Mean fracture resistance (N) values were measured for each group.

- **Statistical analysis-** Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 21, Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) was performed for each group. Two-way ANOVA was used to compare fracture resistance amongst groups. Post hoc multiple comparison test was done with TUKEY HSD for pairwise comparison.

Result

The study compared three different combinations of medicaments (TAP, Nitrofurantoin, and Fosfomycin) and sealers (AH Plus and Bioceramic) checking the fracture resistance of teeth.

The strongest combination was TAP + AH Plus, meaning this mix made teeth the most resistant to breaking.

The weakest was Fosfomycin + Bioceramic, meaning this mix gave the least fracture strength.

When looking at just the sealer type:

AH Plus generally performed a bit better than Bioceramic for all medicaments.

This difference was smallest for Nitrofurantoin (almost the same) and largest with Fosfomycin (where AH Plus was much stronger).

When looking at the medicament type:

TAP always produced the strongest results, Nitrofurantoin came second, followed by Fosfomycin was the weakest.

- **Tested combinations and mean fracture loads (N):**
 - **Group 1A: TAP + AH Plus — 1236.4**
 - **Group 1B: TAP + Bioceramic — 1199.7**
 - **Group 2A: Nitrophenotone + AH Plus — 1137.8**
 - **Group 2B: Nitrophenotone + Bioceramic — 1135.2**
 - **Group 3A: Fosfomycin + AH Plus — 1060.0**
 - **Group 3B: Fosfomycin + Bioceramic — 993.3**

DISCUSSION

Numerous previous studies confirm that the type of sealer and medicament greatly impacts the fracture resistance of treated teeth.

Epoxy resin-based sealers such as AH Plus have generally been shown to enhance fracture resistance due to their adhesive properties and ability to penetrate dentinal tubules, supporting findings from the present study where AH Plus outperformed bioceramic sealers across all medicaments.

Bioceramic sealers also show benefits, such as chemical bonding with dentin and formation of hydroxyapatite, but their performance can vary depending on the combination of medicament and technique used.

- the superior performance of triple antibiotic paste (TAP) with AH Plus matches existing literature emphasizing the combined effect of effective disinfection and strong sealer-dentin adhesion to optimize fracture resistance.
- Although bioceramic sealers present promising results, their interaction with certain medicaments, notably fosfomycin, may result in reduced fracture strength.
- The overall clinical implication is that optimal fracture resistance depends on choosing compatible medicament-sealer combinations and considering both material properties and procedural techniques for best outcomes.

Conclusion

- TAP combined with AH Plus resin sealer yields the highest fracture resistance of root dentin among the tested combinations.
- AH Plus tends to outperform Bioceramic for the same medicament, particularly with Fosfomycin.
- Fosfomycin groups generally produce the lowest fracture resistance, indicating a potential weakening effect relative to TAP and Nitrophenotone under these conditions.

INTERVENTION TO BE MADE ON PATIENT OR ANY OTHER HUMAN OR ANIMALS: -

No intervention on any human or animals will be required to be done.

REFERENCE STYLE: - Vancouver referring

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